

ANTECEDENTS OF CUSTOMER ROYALTY OF DUTY-FREE SHOPS IN THAILAND

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ABSTRACT

A duty-free shop is a retail outlet whose goods are exempt from the payment of certain local or national taxes and duties on the requirement that the goods sold will be sold to travelers who will take them out of the country. Tourists travelling around the world will experience in buying duty free goods at the captioned shops in international airports, seaports and in town causing an increase of their competitiveness. During the past few years when Thailand has faced the pandemic of Covid-19, the duty-free shops have unavoidably been affected due to lock-down measure whereas this captioned business lacks of market power, customer royalty enhancement and marketing strategy to achieve its operating results. This research is therefore aims to 1) examine the level of variables; satisfaction, digital marketing strategy, information quality, product value recognition, service quality and customer royalty of duty-free shops in Thailand, 2) examine the influence of the aforementioned variables towards customer royalty of duty-free shops in Thailand, and 3) develop the customer royalty model for duty-free shops in Thailand. The mixed research method between the quantitative and qualitative terms was conducted. In view of quantitative one, the sample group consisted of 400 customers of duty-free shops in Thailand and sampling size was defined based on the multi-stage sampling method with 20-time criteria of the observed variables. Data collection was conducted through questionnaires that were later analyzed by the structural equation modelling. For the qualitative term, an in-depth interview was made with the main group of 20 informants that were customers of duty-free shops in Thailand. The findings revealed that 1) satisfaction, digital marketing strategy, information technology quality, product value recognition, service quality and customer royalty of duty-free shops in Thailand were all at high level, 2) the satisfaction, digital marketing strategy, information technology quality, product value recognition, service quality influenced the customer royalty of duty-free shops in Thailand with statistical significance value of .05, and 3) the model for customer royalty to duty-free shops as developed by the researcher was called "2S2QRL Model" (S = Digital Marketing Strategy, Q = Information Quality, Q = Service Quality, S = Satisfaction, R = Product Value Recognition, L = Customer Loyalty). In addition, the qualitative findings revealed that to enhance the customer royalty of duty-free shops in Thailand, the entrepreneurs should apply the digital marketing strategy with innovation and technology to effectively respond to their customer requirements. The research findings can be further applied as a guideline for policy determination of duty-free shop business to promote sustainable customer royalty of these captioned shops in Thailand.

Keywords: Antecedents/Customer Royalty of Duty-Free Shops/Thailand

INTRODUCTION

The growth of duty-free goods around the world is due to an increase in the numbers of low-cost airlines and tourists. The purchasing power of tourists has increased sales in duty-free shops at the airports, ports and retail outlets in the city. In addition, the population of the middle class is constantly increasing, causing consumer spending to grow accordingly. Especially in

tourism, it is the activity of the population that indicates the world economy in which the global retail market is highly competitive. Organizations involved in the duty-free sale of goods have pricing that creates a market advantage, such as driving an aggressive marketing strategy and launching innovative new products based on consumer demand)Market Research.com; Global Duty-free Retailing Market - 2019-2026(.

Building customer loyalty requires a marketing strategy that constructs understanding and recognition of the value of the product from quality business information that is easy to use, accurate and complete. Such information help customers and tourists decide to buy duty-free products, including quality and customized services according to the needs of customers in a fast time to meet the needs of all target customers. When the customers are satisfied, they will repurchase, recommend, have a good attitude towards all types of products in the duty-free shop business and do not change their mind to buy the same products suggested by other businesses. This is the loyalty that duty-free shops expect to build market competitiveness)Hussein, et al., 2018; Jin, et al, 2020; Hong, et al., 2019(.

Furthermore, improving the quality of information to be up-to-date, accurate and complete makes customers perceive the value of goods and services more. Pham et al. (2018) found that there was a relationship between convenience of the perceived information and repeat purchase intentions of customers in online shopping. The results also showed that perceived value played the important role in direct influence on repeat purchase intention, leading customer satisfaction, customer loyalty towards product and business. Perceiving the value of products from the platform in digital marketing channels that duty-free shops want to communicate to customers the value and benefits of products and services can create customer satisfaction, good image for the business and its products (Samiee & Chirapanda, 2019) and repeat purchase with business loyalty (Chou & Chen, 2018). Repeat purchase intention arises from the recognition of the value of a product in terms of both quality and service that customers receive from a business, resulting in customer loyalty. It was also found that the intention of consumers to use the service and to buy goods was due to the perceived value of goods and services (Chen et al., 2018), which is considered a business marketing advantage. Service quality affects customer satisfaction in repeat purchases.

The Thai government therefore has a plan for creative and cultural tourism by proposing guidelines to develop environmental factors to facilitate creativity in order to improve tourism products and services (Setthachotsombut & Aunyawong, 2020). It likewise strengthens the potential of entrepreneurs and personnel in the tourism industry to provide skills and knowledge in business throughout the tourism supply chain (Sooksai et al., 2022). Innovation and technology have been applied in business administration and marketing to create differentiation and uniqueness of products and services in accordance with the needs of the tourism market (Hiranphaet et al., 2022). The tourism market has been promoted through creative communication of stories in digital marketing channels. Tourism in Thailand is continuously expanding and has an increase in the numbers of tourists and tourism income, including the growth of networked businesses with tourism, the expansion of the global tourism market, the low-cost airline business and the use of digital marketing communication

technology to reach customers easily and quickly (Nopphakate & Aunyawong, 2022). Hence, there is more intense competition for ASEAN countries. The tourism strategy is used as the main strategy for the country's economic development. Thus, Thailand must enhance its competitiveness and create a variety in the context of tourism in accordance with the needs of tourists such as tourism products and tourism services. Such promotion will affect the tourism industry in creating and distributing income and develop the country's competitiveness (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2017). It can be concluded that customer satisfaction is related to product quality, service quality and valuable store features (El-Adly, 2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Marketing Strategy

Digital marketing strategy is a modern marketing method that reaches more customers' needs with ease, quickness anytime and anywhere. This makes it an essential tool for building a competitive advantage in the modern business. Duty-free shops adopt digital marketing strategies to enhance the potential of businesses in customer service according to the modern consumer behavior. Modern marketing communications, social media orientation, marketing content creation potential are focused on online marketing influencers. Online reputation management and marketing development in terms of both ideas and practices occur in tandem with the evolution of humanity all along. Changing the business environment to meet more modern customers by using innovation and technology create convenience in accessing goods and services without limitation of time and place. It can create customer satisfaction, affecting customer loyalty towards the business. Social influence as a guide Social presence in digital marketing strategies creates a real consumer viewing experience. This will help increase consumer intention to find and subscribe. Such strategies affect search and subscription intention, including purchase intention. Consumer viewing is a factor in favor of business success (Kerdpitak et al., 2022; Pham et. al., 2018). The study of the relationship among convenience, perceived value and repeat purchase intention in online shopping found that electronic commerce is an increasingly popular trend in the modern economy in parallel with the development of the Internet. E-commerce has evolved greatly, allowing businesses expansion in the world because of the convenience in online shopping, including access, search, evaluation, transaction and post-purchase convenience. All information dimensions have a direct impact on the perceived value and repurchase intention. Digital marketing strategy is a strategy that truly meets the needs of customers because it can provide quality customer service in terms of processes, systems, and quality of information. It makes customers satisfied, especially the quality of complete and correct electronic services of information systems, resulting in intentional repurchasing (Kerdpitak, 2022a; Alfian et al., 2019).

Perceived Value of Product

Customers' perceived value of product through the various channels that duty-free shops communicate with customers allows customers to plan their purchases according to their needs. Most of the content of the product will be on the platform of the business that communicates

to customers in digital channels, which is a convenient and quick channel to reach customers. In addition, perceived value of product will include the quality of the product expected by customers. It is information that customers know about the value or quality of the product for utilization. If the customer's expectations are met, satisfaction will occur and lead to a purchase decision (Gupta, 2018). Perceived value of product is important for customers to understand the quality of the product and its price. It shows the benefits of implications. Perceived benefits influence consumers' intention to buy a product. It refers to perceived value of product as an indication of the product quality that customers know before purchasing. The product that is beneficial to the customer is an incentive to shop with confidence and trust in business and duty-free products (Wang & Farquhar, 2018; Correia et al., 2018).

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the positive attitude that customers have about products and businesses through the perceived value of product from the information that the duty-free shop business communicates through marketing channels to various customers both online and offline. Digital marketing channels can reach the needs of all target customers to create awareness of the service quality that customers want and expect with high-quality marketing information systems. Satisfaction is the impression the customer receives from something positively tangible, such as the service of a business person, compassion, assisting customers with a willingness to create a good image for customers (Aunyawong et al., 2020; Phrapratanporn et al., 2019). The roles of service quality dimensions can increase customer satisfaction and has a positive effect on customer value. This will lead to customer response in making a purchase decision and can create customer satisfaction (Vukadin et al., 2018). Customer satisfaction resulting from digital marketing channels has changed the business environment to meet more modern customers by using innovation and technology to facilitate access to goods and services without limitation of time and place (Nguyen et al., 2018). Satisfaction also affects customer loyalty from the corporate image, service quality and perceived value (Song et al., 2019). Customer satisfaction arising from obtaining relevant information based on customer needs for purchasing decisions and using service affects the business from the perceived value of products and services. Satisfaction is the positive feelings and attitudes of customers from digital marketing channels with complete information about products and services. It helps to make purchasing decisions faster with big data in customer service. Retailers will gain a competitive advantage over their competitors (Kerdpitak, 2022; El-Adly, 2019).

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty comes from the fact that customers are aware of the value and benefits of accurate products and services every time (Waiyavat et al., 2022). Customers perceive the quality of the product from the digital platform of the business and the quality of the product after use. When customers find that the value of the product meets or exceeds their expectations, the good image of the customer to the business will occur, leading to a positive attitude towards all types of business products (Wang & Farquhar, 2018). Customers' perceived value of service causes to perceive the benefits, leading to the intention to use the service. The quality of the product that the customer wants to buy is an important part that the

customer should know how to use, indications, benefits and precautions. This allows customers to plan in purchasing and obtain more productive uses (Polas et al., 2019). Perceived value is related to customer engagement in marketing communications because in today market, companies expect their customers to not only consume what they have to offer but they still want participation in digital marketing communications (Itani et al., 2019). The customers' perceived value contributes to greater trust in the business and has a direct positive effect on customer loyalty (El-Adly, 2019). Tourist perceptions of duty-free shops' goods and services help to increase the attitude of the brand and have a positive effect on word of mouth (Kim et al., 2019). It can make tourists choose to buy travel products according to their needs because letting customers know the product before purchasing is an information in making a purchasing decision that does not cause the customer to risk purchasing the product. This demonstrates the sincerity and integrity of the business by using the platform in digital marketing channels (Kelly & Lawlor, 2019; Xu et al., 2021). Loyalty to the business is also driven by the key customer expectations and caused by the quality of service that the business provides to the customers of the duty-free shop, such as responsiveness, response time and customized services that can reach the needs of every target customer (Chatzopoulou et al., 2022). Providing custom-made customer service can build trust and confidence in using more services, especially in airport retail environments (Caglayan & Afacan, 2021).

Quality of Information

The quality of information is an important factor in building customer understanding about the goods and services of duty-free shop business. The information is communicated through a variety of channels, including digital marketing channels that customers can access easily and quickly (Pintuma et al., 2020). Quality information must have features that are easy to use, easy to understand, complete and correct. The quality of information can increase the shopping value, trust and decision of customers online through the ease to access and understand information. This enables customers to make purchasing decisions quickly and conveniently from online purchases (Nghia et al., 2020). The quality of information is complete information for product types, product context, price, distribution, trading method, promotions and other things that allow customers to benefit from being informed in order to make a purchase decision or to use a channel to make a purchase from the platform in an appropriate manner for online consumers (Xu et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This research was a mixed methods research between quantitative research and qualitative research. The population was 6,702,396 duty-free shop customers in Thailand (Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2021). In the quantitative study, the sample size was estimated from the number of observed variables in the ratio of 1 to 20. In this research, there were 20 observed variables. The researchers therefore determined the 400 samples using a multi-stage sampling from customers of duty-free shops in Thailand (Nunnally et al., 1967; Jackson, 2003; Hair et al., 2011)

The sampling was done using a multistage sampling method in order to obtain the sample, as detailed as follows:

Step 1: Thai airports were divided into 6 areas: Suvarnabhumi Airport, Don Mueang Airport, Chiang Mai Airport, Hat Yai Airport, Phuket Airport, Mae Fah Luang Airport and Chiang Rai Airport.

Step 2: In each airport, simple random sampling was used to obtain 67 tourists who use duty-free shops in 4 airports: Suvarnabhumi Airport, Don Mueang Airport, Chiang Mai Airport and Phuket Airport, including 66 tourists in Hat Yai Airport, Mae Fah Luang Airport and Chiang Rai Airport, totaling a sample of 400 tourists.

Step 3: The sampling was conducted with 67 tourists who use duty-free shops of Suvarnabhumi Airport, 67 tourists in Don Mueang Airport, 67 tourists in Chiang Mai Airport, and 67 tourists in Phuket Airport, 66 tourists in Hat Yai Airport, 66 tourists in Mae Fah Luang Airport and 66 tourists in Chiang Rai Airport, totaling a sample of 400 tourists.

In quantitative research, the researchers used questionnaires as a research tool to collect data, while the tool used in qualitative research was the interview form. Statistics used in data analysis included descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling (SEM).

RESULTS

This study used preliminary data analysis before to test the relationship between variables (Adamski et al., 2005). Preliminary data analysis is the crucial part of every data analysis because it is important to remove the errors in the data before data analysis. Preliminary data analysis is given in Table 1 in which standard deviation, normality of the data and p-value is given.

Table 1: Statistical test of empirical variables (n=400)

Variables	\bar{X}	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
MDCOM	4.04	.68	16.83	-.378	-6.616	43.920	.000
SCORI	4.00	.67	16.75	-.021	-5.388	29.026	.000
CTCRA	4.12	.71	17.23	-1.193	-9.729	96.067	.000
INFLU	3.98	.74	18.59	-.965	-4.630	22.371	.000
REPUL	4.02	.65	16.17	-.165	-3.696	13.688	.001
RESPO	4.03	.77	19.11	-2.195	-1.391	6.755	.034
RESTM	4.12	.71	17.23	-2.055	-3.443	16.078	.000
CUSMZ	4.17	.75	17.99	-2.939	-3.042	17.893	.000
ESAL	4.13	.69	16.71	-1.292	-8.261	69.905	.000
ESUDS	4.05	.77	19.01	-2.045	-4.279	22.490	.000
COPLT	4.08	.78	19.12	-2.466	-3.612	19.126	.000
ACCU	4.10	.70	17.07	-1.041	-8.810	78.705	.000
PLDBU	4.14	.69	16.67	-2.119	-2.688	11.716	.003
RCQLT	4.15	.71	17.11	-2.436	-2.564	12.510	.002
CHDIG	4.28	.67	15.65	-3.230	-2.769	18.102	.000
INFMK	4.19	.73	17.42	-3.010	-3.492	21.257	.000

BUYAG	4.20	.70	16.67	-2.947	-2.633	15.618	.000
ATTBU	4.25	.68	16.00	-2.527	-8.065	71.437	.000
NOCHG	4.22	.70	16.59	-2.927	-2.083	12.907	.002
RECMD	4.24	.76	17.92	-3.730	-2.835	21.949	.000

Note: Chi-square χ^2 (with statistical significance)P-value <.05) indicates a non-normal distribution.

The results of checking the normal curve distribution (Normal Score) of the empirical variables studied in the structural equation model using chi-square (χ^2) depicted statistical significance ($p > .05$) for all variables. So, all empirical variables had non-normal distribution. In addition, a large sample ($n \geq 400$) could statistically consent that the data measured with the rating scale questionnaire had a normal curve distribution, according to The Central Limit Theorem as suggested by Kelloway (1998).

Such results may result in assessing whether the model was empirically fit. The chi-square (χ^2) was problematic, so the researchers solved the problem by estimating fit using the ratio of chi-square (χ^2) to degrees of freedom (df). If the value was less than 5.00, the model was fit to empirical data, although the chi-square (χ^2) test was statistically significant (p -value < .05) (Wanichbancha, 2013; Hair, et al., 2006).

Table 2: Factor Loadings. (n = 400)

Variables	Factor Loading λ (Error θ (t	R ²
Digital Marketing Strategy (DGMST)				
Using Modern Marketing Communications (MDCOM)	.80	.36	18.24	.64
Social Media Orientation (SCORI)	.87	.24	21.39	.76
Marketing Content Creation Potential (CTCRA)	.83	.31	20.05	.69
Online Marketing Influencer (INFLU)	.84	.30	19.96	.70
Online Reputation Management (REPUL)	.80	.36	18.1	.64
$\rho_c = .92 \rho_v = .69$				
Service Quality (SERQU)				
Responsiveness (RESPO)	.71	.49	14.47	.51
Response Time (RESTM)	.76	.42	15.47	.58
Service Customization (CUSMZ)	.79	.37	16.17	.63
$\rho_c = .80 \rho_v = .57$				
Quality of Information (QUIFM)				
Ease to Apply (ESAL)	.65	.58	13.54	.42
Easy Understanding (ESUDS)	.85	.28	18.09	.72
Completeness (COPLT)	.82	.34	17.19	.66
Accuracy (ACCU)	.70	.51	13.99	.49
$\rho_c = .84 \rho_v = .57$				

Perceived Value of Product)VALPD)					
	Digital Platform of Business)PLDBU)	.95	.10	25.34	.90
	Received Quality (RCQLT)	.76	.43	17.28	.57
$\rho_c = .85 \quad \rho_v = .74$					
Satisfaction)STFN)					
	Channel of Digital Marketing (CHDIG)	.94	.11	25.14	.89
	Information in Marketing)INFMK)	.58	.67	12.00	.33
$\rho_c = .75 \quad \rho_v = .61$					
Customer Loyalty for Duty-Free Shops in Thailand)LYDFS)					
	Buying Again (BUYAG)	.55	.70	10.68	.30
	Having a positive attitude towards all types of business products (ATTBU)	.59	.65	10.66	.35
	Not change the mind to buy products with other businesses (NOCHG)	.89	.21	16.72	.79
	Recommendations in both online and offline (RECMD)	.75	.43	14.44	.57
$\rho_c = .80 \quad \rho_v = .50$					

Table 3. Measurement Model (n=400)

Dependent variables	R ²	Effects	Independent Variables				
			Perceived Value of Product)VALPD)	Satisfaction)STFN)	Digital Marketing Strategy)DGMST)	Service Quality)SERQU)	Quality of Information)QUIFM)
Perceived Value of Product)VALPD)	.72	DE	-	-	.56*(7.69)	.74*(6.07)	.66*(6.82)
		IE	-	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	-	.56*(7.69)	.74*(6.07)	.66*(6.82)
Satisfaction)STFN)	.82	DE	.65*(8.55)	-	.48*(6.11)	.50*(3.69)	.24*(3.96)
		IE	-	-	.31*(6.57)	.31*(6.65)	.41*(6.67)
		TE	.65*(8.55)	-	.79*(7.14)	.81*(5.95)	.65*(3.78)
Customer Loyalty for Duty-Free Shops in Thailand)LYDFS)	.89	DE	-	.64*(18.55)	-	-	-
		IE	.75*(8.56)	-	.69*(7.14)	.64*(6.00)	.66*(3.79)
		TE	.75*(8.56)	.64*(18.55)	.69*(7.14)	.64*(6.00)	.66*(3.79)
$\chi^2 = 214.73 \text{ df} = 113 \text{ p-value} = .00000, \chi^2 / \text{df} = 1.90, \text{RMSEA} = .047, \text{RMR} = .016, \text{SRMR} = .032, \text{CFI} = .99, \text{GFI} = .95, \text{AGFI} = .91, \text{CN} = 267.85$							

*Statistically Significant level of .05

Note: The t-test statistical values were shown in parentheses. If the values were not between -1.96 and 1.96, they have statistically significant level of .05.

Figure 1: Adjusted Model (n=400)

The results of the analysis of the adjusted structural equation model found that it was fit to the empirical data ($\chi^2 = 214.73$ $df = 113$ $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.90$, $RMSEA = .047$, $RMR = .016$, $SRMR = .032$, $CFI = .99$, $GFI = .95$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 267.85$). The researchers, therefore, relied on the estimation of parameters in the model and reported the equation that occurs in the model both in the part that reports the results of the equation and the measurement model part. It portrayed the factor loadings of the observed variables with their latent variables. In addition, the structural model reported the relationship among latent variables according to the research hypotheses.

Interpretation of equations in measurement models and structural model considered three important statistic tests: 1) R^2 was the rate of the ability to use latent variable to describe the variance of the observed variable, which factors of the latent variable, 2) the standardized factor loadings or standardized solution (λ) was an approximation of the parameter estimation of the factor/correlation between the observed variables and the latent variables, 3) standard error was the variation of the measurement error of the observed variable, and 4) the t-test was used to analyze the statistically significant reliability of the measurement by which the t-test greater than 1.96 indicated statistically significant level of .05, while the t-test between -1.96 – 1.96 was not statistically significant. The results of the measurement equation and the structural equation that described the structural equation model were reported sequentially.

CONCLUSION

The results have revealed that satisfaction, digital marketing strategy, quality of information, perceived value of product, service quality and customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand are at a high level. The relationship path equations of independent variables that have a direct effect on dependent variables in the adjust model have shown that digital marketing strategy, service quality and the quality of information have a direct effect on the perceived value of product, with statistically significant level of .05, explaining 72% of the variance. Perceived

value of the product, digital marketing strategy, service quality and quality of information have a direct effect on satisfaction, with statistically significant level of .05 level, explaining 82% of the variance. Satisfaction has a direct effect on customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand, with a statistically significant level .05, explaining 89 percent of the variance.

The relationship path equations of exogenous latent variables that have a total effect on endogenous latent variables (Reduced equations) in the adjusted model have portrayed that the exogenous latent variables, consisting of digital marketing strategy, service quality, and quality of information, have a total effect on perceived value of product with statistically significant level of .05, explaining 72% of the variance. The exogenous latent variables, involving digital marketing strategy, service quality, and quality of information, have a total effect on satisfaction, with statistically significant level of .05, explaining 81% of the variance. The exogenous latent variables, comprising digital marketing strategy, service quality and quality of information, have a total effect on customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand, with statistically significant level of .05, explaining 88 percent of the variance.

After obtaining the findings according to the research objectives, the researchers therefore developed the 2S2QRL Model (S = Digital Marketing Strategy, Q = Quality of Information, Q = Service Quality, S = Satisfaction, R = Perceived Value of Product, L = Customer Loyalty) as a model of customer loyalty in the duty-free shops in Thailand.

Policy recommendations

Policy recommendations that are important in building customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand are as follows:

- 1) The government should formulate a policy of cooperation with relevant organizations in all sectors in developing customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand.
- 2) Relevant agencies should formulate integrated policies and plans to effectively strengthen the customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand by improving satisfaction, digital marketing strategies, quality of information, perceived value of product and service quality.
- 3) Governments and related agencies should have integrated actions to develop satisfaction, digital marketing strategies, quality of information, perceived value of product and service quality to promote customer loyalty for duty-free shops in Thailand in a sustainably academic way.
- 4) Government by the Department of Business Development, the Ministry of Commerce, and the organizations involved in building customer loyalty for duty-free shops should develop the businesses to meet the needs and expectations of customers to promote confidence and loyalty to duty-free shop businesses in Thailand.

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